

REFLECTIONS ON THE FIELD: EXPERIENCES OF EARLY CAREER DIGITAL PRESERVATION PRACTITIONERS

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Abstract – This panel addresses Tūhono (Connect) for three practitioners of digital preservation. Orientating our discussion from perspectives of Black, Indigenous, People of Color (BIPOC) who live and work in the United States, we examine our paths into digital preservation and the roadblocks and detours we've faced. How did we get where we are and who helped us? Where do we see our careers going? What does this path look like to other BIPOC information workers and how do we connect with them? These questions are asked in the context of a country experiencing a political pushback against equity efforts.

Submission Type – Panel

Keywords – Community, Skills, Engagement

Conference Topics – Tūhono - Connect.

I. INTRODUCTION

This panel of three early career practitioners will discuss their experiences developing their careers in digital preservation, grounding their perspectives as Black, Indigenous, People of Color (BIPOC) living and working in the United States. The panelists will focus on the role of their identity at work, linking their professional skills to community engagement, and leaning on peer mentoring for skills development.

In light of the [DPC Report on Mental Health and Wellbeing in Digital Preservation](#) [1], and inspired by the 2024 Birds of a Feather session “The Challenges of Working in Digital Preservation and the Impact on Practitioner Mental Health and Wellbeing” [2] talking about the holistic experiences of the people working in digital preservation is an important step in

supporting the community at large. Sharing our experiences, though rooted in a very U.S.-focused perspective, may provide insights for a broader audience facing similar challenges. By openly discussing the challenges faced in the field by marginalized groups, we can start to address the issues.

II. PANEL OBJECTIVES

- To examine the dynamics that shape the experiences of BIPOC professionals face in the digital preservation field
- To discuss mentorship, peer networks, and career progression strategies for BIPOC practitioners, particularly in navigating underrepresented spaces within digital preservation.

III. PANEL DISCUSSION TOPICS

This panel will delve into the challenge, strategies and successes of BIPOC professionals face within the field of digital preservation. Panelists will reflect on personal and professional experiences and discuss the hurdles of working in an environment that lacks representation. The conversation will examine the importance of mentorship, community engagement, and navigating a predominantly white field.

A. Identity and Representation

One of the challenges faced by BIPOC professionals in digital preservation is the negotiation of identity. Panelists will discuss the complexities of being recognized as a person of color before being acknowledged for their expertise and how this dynamic can influence career progression. In many professional settings, the perception of skills and competencies is often overshadowed by racial identity. The discussion will also address the challenge of limited representation in leadership roles within the digital preservation community and how this underrepresentation impacts the direction and inclusivity of the field. Finally, panelists will explore the importance of mentors who understand not only the technicalities of the profession but also the unique experiences of BIPOC professionals navigating spaces that may not always be inclusive.

B. Community Engagement

Community engagement can be explained as a defined relationship between two or more entities that participate in and contribute to the growth and preservation of various activities. Although the practice of digital preservation is complex, practitioners have proven that the process can be reshaped to fit the needs of its constituents. BIPOC practitioners interested in the preservation of digital objects, both digitized and born-digital, archival materials, or published research can apply theories and best practices as a method to support community members.

A focus on professional development will allow for BIPOC practitioners to merge their experiences into their work, such as networking on a local, national, and global scale; leaning on scholarship created by practitioners; curating courses; the pursuit to continuing education through certification or courses that propel knowledge about programming, tools, or hardware; and securing a supportive network of colleagues.

A combination of professional goals that develop applicable skills and frequent engagement with communities can assist BIPOC professionals in reaching their professional goals. This discussion will explore how practitioners can merge their lived experiences with their professional goals to create a more inclusive and community-focused approach to digital preservation.

C. Career Progression

Mentorship is a key component of career development but a person brings more than their work experience to the relationship. For BIPOC librarians and archivists, finding mentors with not just similar career paths but also life experience is one of the most beneficial ways to advance in the field. The skewed racial representation within the field, especially within the focus of digital preservation, makes finding an experienced practitioner of color to act as a mentor challenging. New professionals rely on peer mentoring, sharing knowledge, experience, and advice across a cohort of similar work experience, to bridge the gaps between work and personhood [3].

Advancing their professional development has also been challenged by starting digital preservation careers during the COVID pandemic and amid lapsed communities and training programs. While other countries such as Canada and the United Kingdom have dedicated resources to digital preservation training, the same resources are not as prolific in the U.S. In discussing how they managed to piece together training opportunities in the field and created their career paths, the panelists hope to share their strategies with the digital preservation community as well as learn from attendees.

Key questions for discussion by the panelists include: 1) How did we get to this point in the field? What have been some key turning points? 2) What motivates you to stay in this work? 3) What opportunities or changes are needed in the field to better support and include BIPOC practitioners?

REFERENCES

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